

GLOBAL REPORT

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CAMPAIGNS

VERSION 1 MARCH 2025

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INTRODUCTION

What is ProBleu?

ProBleu is a European initiative dedicated to promoting ocean and freshwater literacy in schools across Europe. Through its funding calls, it supports educational institutions in developing Blue School projects, which integrate water-related themes into their curriculum and activities. The project aligns with the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters", fostering knowledge, engagement, and action towards sustainable water stewardship.

Communication & dissemination strategy: The ProBleu funnel approach

ProBleu's communication and dissemination campaigns are strategically designed to maximize engagement from schools, teachers, and stakeholders. These efforts follow a marketing funnel approach, guiding audiences through different stages—from initial awareness to full participation. In ProBleu's case, this funnel includes:

- Social media and outreach emails to generate awareness.
- Newsletter subscriptions and info sessions to nurture interest.
- Applications to funding calls as an engagement milestone.
- Re-applications and Blue School accreditation to ensure long-term commitment.

By structuring outreach efforts in this way, ProBleu ensures an effective and scalable engagement model that grows the network of Blue Schools across Europe.

About this report

This document presents a data-driven analysis of ProBleu's communication and dissemination efforts, specifically focused on funding call campaigns. The report compiles insights from a Google Looker Studio dashboard, which integrates data from Google Sheets and tracking tools. The interactive online version allows users to apply filters to extract key insights, track the performance of different outreach strategies, and compare results across funding calls.

This analysis serves as a valuable tool for identifying improvements, refining strategies, and optimizing future campaigns. By capitalizing on past efforts, ProBleu can allocate resources more effectively and ensure impact in its outreach actions.

Furthermore, these insights can be shared with other EU projects, strengthening collective knowledge and best practices in science communication and engagement.

CAMPAIGNS

Call ▾

Consortium Partner ▾

	Country	N° People Reac...
1.	All	51.196
2.	Spain	55.868
3.	United Kingdom	38.539
4.	Portugal	2.561
5.	Croatia	10.404
6.	Italy	197.695
7.	Finland	37
8.	Ireland	9.235
9.	Germany	322
10.	Moldova	27
11.	Austria	8.889
12.	Latvia	30
13.	Greece	62
14.	Denmark	35
15.	Slovenia	15.019
16.	Iceland	19
17.	Armenia	2.780
18.	France	61.362
19.	Albania	2.790
20.	Faroe Islands	1.587

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	Channel	N° People ...
1.	Email	74.136
2.	Social Media	323.818
3.	In-person	9.437
4.	Event	419
5.	Facebook	46.529
6.	Webinar	404
7.	Newsletter	1.400
8.	Website	3.101
9.	INOVA+'s LinkedIn	39.681
10.	LinkedIn	1.002
11.	Zoom	1
12.	Inovas+'s newsletter	1.539
13.	Social Media	15.143
14.	Video call	2
15.	Whatsapp	241
16.	SERN's LinkedIn	1.713
17.	Instagram	1.000
18.	Other	1
19.	Twitter	1.000
20.	Youtube	254

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	Consortium Part...	N° People Reach...
1.	CSIC	403.715
2.	Inova+	53.912
3.	Earthwatch	9.717
4.	OCT	49.617
5.	PML	1.158
6.	KTU	2.701
7.	Innova+	3

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PEOPLE REACHED by Country

Call ▾

Consortium Partner ▾

Effort distribution

Reached Countries

44

	Countries	3rd ▾
1.	United Kingdom	17.312
2.	Serbia	12.001
3.	Spain	8.451
4.	Albania	2.740
5.	Armenia	2.730
6.	Ireland	2.122
7.	Tunisia	2.112
8.	Croatia	1.992

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Unreached Countries

1

	Countries	3rd ▾
1.	Montenegro	0

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WEBSITE VISITS
(Call Open Periods)

FUNDING CALLS

WEBSITE DOWNLOADS (Call Open Periods)

Call

	Content	Unique Downloads ▾
1.	Call for Proposals 3	1.708
2.	Description Form 3 Word	1.274
3.	Project Template Example 3 Wo...	1.125
4.	DoH 3	772
5.	Call of proposal 2nd call	700
6.	Project Template 2nd call	517
7.	Description Form 3 Pdf	401
8.	Factsheet Call 3 English	229
9.	3rd Call Infosession Presentation	195
10.	Call of proposal	188
11.	Templates-and-guidance-to-dev...	168
12.	Declaration of Honour 2nd call	167
13.	Project Template Example	162
14.	Project brainstorming template ...	152
15.	Info Session PPT 2nd call	149
16.	Results call 2	128
17.	Project Template	114
	Total	9.532

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FUNDING CALLS
APPLICANT SOURCE per call

Call ▼

Total Applications
474

FUNDING CALLS

APPLICANT COUNTRIES per call

Total Applications

474

Total Countries

37

FUNDING CALLS

APPLICANT COUNTRIES Call comparison

	Applicant Country	1st	2nd	3rd ① ▾	Total ② ▾
1.	Greece	0	11	99	110
2.	Lithuania	19	4	26	49
3.	Spain	30	28	24	82
4.	Romania	1	0	24	25
5.	North Macedonia	0	4	20	24
6.	Türkiye	0	4	16	20
7.	Portugal	8	19	11	38
8.	Italy	2	2	10	14
9.	Albania	0	2	8	10
10.	France	3	1	6	10
11.	Armenia	0	0	6	6
12.	Georgia	2	1	5	8
13.	Poland	0	1	5	6
14.	Finland	0	0	5	5
15.	Latvia	0	0	5	5
16.	Serbia	2	1	4	7
17.	Croatia	0	1	4	5
18.	Morocco	1	0	3	4
19.	Republic of Cyprus	0	0	3	3
20.	Moldova	0	0	3	3
21.	United Kingdom	1	4	2	7
	Total	80	87	307	474

FUNDING CALLS

Nurturing: Returning Applicant Schools

STATUS ▼

STATUS	Funded Call	Applicant Schools
Only 3rd Call	Not Funded	263
	Call 3	32
	Subtotal	295
Only 2nd Call	Not Funded	29
	Call 2	25
	Subtotal	54
Only 1st Call	Not Funded	42
	Call 1	11
	Subtotal	53
Returning 2	Not Funded	14
	Call 2	10
	Subtotal	24
Total		438

FUNDING CALLS

Funded Projects per Country

Funded Schools
79

Funded Countries
31

FUNDING CALLS

Success Rate per Country

	Applicant Country	Applications	Total Funded ① ▾	Success Ratio ② ▾
1.	Spain	82	18	21,95%
2.	Portugal	38	7	18,42%
3.	Greece	110	6	5,45%
4.	Italy	14	5	35,71%
5.	Morocco	4	3	75,00%
6.	Latvia	5	3	60,00%
7.	United Kingdom	7	3	42,86%
8.	France	10	3	30,00%
9.	Sweden	4	2	50,00%
10.	Estonia	5	2	40,00%
11.	Poland	6	2	33,33%
12.	Armenia	6	2	33,33%
13.	Albania	10	2	20,00%
14.	North Macedonia	24	2	8,33%
15.	Romania	25	2	8,00%
16.	Lithuania	49	2	4,08%
17.	Israel	1	1	100,00%
18.	Faroe Islands	1	1	100,00%
19.	Czech Republic	1	1	100,00%
20.	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	1	100,00%
21.	Tunisia	2	1	50,00%
22.	Slovakia	2	1	50,00%

NEXT STEPS

This report has been shared before the final funding call. Insights gained so far allow us to refine our approach and implement strategic adjustments to maximize the impact of the last phase.

Key takeaways:

- Proven engagement growth: The structured communication funnel has significantly contributed to a steady increase in applications, culminating in a threefold increase in the third call.
- Effective outreach channels: social media campaigns, direct email outreach, and institutional partnerships are the most effective drivers of engagement, particularly when combined with local-level networking.
- Word of mouth power: globally, 33% of applicants have learned about funding calls through word of mouth or a colleague, reinforcing the importance of community-building efforts.
- The role of established networks: Institutions and NGOs remain among the most significant referral sources. Many of these organizations are already partners of ProBleu consortium members, underlining the importance of leveraging existing networks for dissemination.

Refinements:

- Expand localized outreach: Strengthen efforts in underrepresented regions through Language Ambassadors and local networks, ensuring a broader geographic reach.
- Enhance re-engagement strategies: Maintain contact with previously interested schools through tailored updates, exclusive webinars, and targeted follow-up actions.
- Strengthen partnerships with institutions and NGOs: Continue to capitalize on existing networks by working closely with educational institutions, environmental NGOs, and local authorities to extend reach.
- Leverage word-of-mouth referrals: Develop content and materials that facilitate peer-to-peer promotion, encouraging more teachers to share funding opportunities within their professional networks.

The strategies refined through ProBleu's experience can inform best practices for other projects working on school engagement, citizen science, and water literacy.